

“Revisiting” North Korea: new species and new records of Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)

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Abstract – Between 1970 and 1995, twenty collecting expeditions were carried out in North Korea by the researchers of the Hungarian Natural History Museum. The majority of the North Korean Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) material is still waiting for identification; in this paper, the subfamily Campopleginae is treated. *Campoletis koreana* sp. nov. and *Meloboris pektusana* sp. nov. are described from North Korea. The following 23 species of the subfamily are reported for the first time from North Korea: *Breviterebra laticlypeata* Kusigemati, 1982, *Campoletis annulata* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Campoletis chlorideae* Uchida, 1957, *Campoletis cognata* (Tschek, 1871), *Campoletis latrator* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Campoletis rugosipropodeum* (Uchida, 1942), *Campoplex alsophilae* (Uchida, 1936), *Casinaria albibasalis* Uchida, 1928, *Casinaria albipalpis* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Casinaria arjuna* Maheshwary et Gupta, 1977, *Casinaria japonica* Kusigemati, 1980, *Casinaria nigripes* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Casinaria partolstoyi* Han, van Achterberg et Chen, 2021, *Casinaria stygia* Tschek, 1871, *Casinaria trochanterator* Aubert, 1960, *Charops bicolor* (Szépligeti, 1906), *Charops striatus* (Uchida, 1932), *Cymodusa koreana* Choi et Lee, 2013, *Cymodusa orientalis* Uchida, 1956, *Lemophagus curtus* Townes, 1965, *Melalophacharops everese* (Uchida, 1957), *Venturia longipropodeum* (Uchida, 1942), and *Venturia mongolica* (Kokujev, 1915), along with remarks on the distribution and the identification of several of these species. With four figures.

Key words – taxonomy, species description, biogeography, Korean Peninsula

INTRODUCTION

Between 1970 and 1995, twenty collecting expeditions were carried out in North Korea (officially the Democratic People’s Republic of Korea) by the researchers of the Hungarian Natural History Museum (HNHM, Budapest). These expeditions resulted for the HNHM the most significant North Korean material among the European natural history museums, as well as many scientific results, including the descriptions of more than 300 new species of insects, published in more than 150 scientific papers (see e.g., PARK & CHOI (2012) for a taxonomic summary).

However, thousands of specimens of various taxa of the collected North Korean material are still waiting for identification in the HNHM; one of these is the family of ichneumon wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). By the time of the North Korean expeditions, there was no specialist of Ichneumonidae among the staff of the HNHM. Therefore, the ichneumon wasp material was not processed, except a small fraction of the subfamily Mesochorinae was examined by South Korean researchers (LEE & SUH 1993). The rest of the North Korean ichneumon wasps remained unidentified. Lately, two species of Hybrizontinae were reported for the first time from North Korea (VAS 2020a); however, the more systematic identification process of the North Korean Ichneumonidae material has just been recently started by the author.

In this paper, part of the North Korean material of the subfamily Campopleginae is treated: two new species are described (*Campoletis koreana* sp. nov. and *Meloboris pektusana* sp. nov.), and 23 species are reported for the first time from North Korea – 14 species among them are recorded for the first time from the Korean Peninsula. Notes for general distribution and identification of the species are also given.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Present study is based on the North Korean Ichneumonidae material deposited in the HNHM. Several hundreds of specimens were identified, of which the ones representing species new to science or new records to the country are published. Taxonomy and nomenclature follow YU & HORSTMANN (1997) and YU *et al.* (2016); complete nomenclatural history and list of synonyms are not repeated here, since they were given in detail in these references. Morphological terminology follows GAULD (1991) and GAULD *et al.* (1997); however, in cases of wing veins the corresponding terminology of TOWNES (1969) is also used. Terminology of body surface sculpturing follows HARRIS (1979). Identifications were established by the author, based on KOKUJEV (1915), UCHIDA (1936, 1942, 1957), PERKINS (1942), KUSIGEMATI (1967, 1972, 1982, 1993), TOWNES (1970), HORSTMANN (1970, 1978, 1979, 1987, 2004), GUPTA & MAHESHWARY (1977), KASPARYAN & DBAR (1985), CHOI & LEE (2008, 2010), CHOI *et al.* (2012, 2013), RIEDEL (2017, 2018a), VAS (2018, 2019a, b, c, d, 2020a, b, c, 2021, 2022, 2023), HAN *et al.* (2021a, b, 2022), HARALDSEIDE (2021), CHOI (2022), VAS *et al.* (2022), and on checking the necessary type material (most importantly types deposited in the Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan). Label data are given verbatim, with additions and explanations in square brackets if necessary.

TAXONOMY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY

Family: Ichneumonidae Latreille, 1802
Subfamily: Campopleginae Förster, 1869

Breviterebra laticlypeata Kusigemati, 1982

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Za-mo san [= Chamo Mt.], 60 km NE from Pyongan [= Pyongyang], No. 186, 18 August 1971, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species was described from Japan (KUSIGEMATI 1982) and found also in the eastern parts of Russia (Khabarovsk Krai, Primorsky Krai) (KASPARYAN & DBAR 1985, YU *et al.* 2016).

Notes on identification – This apparently rare species is known by relatively few specimens; therefore, its intraspecific variability is poorly known. The following information might be useful to the identification: the hind femur of the Korean specimen is pale orange-brown, while that of the Japanese holotype specimen is darker, chestnut-brown; fore and middle coxae are apically extensively orange-coloured, basally dark in the Korean specimen, while those are more extensively dark-coloured in the holotype; the median section of posterior transverse carina is more or less weakened medially (also in the holotype specimen), however it is neither mentioned nor depicted by KUSIGEMATI (1982); pilosity of metasoma is virtually evenly dense from second tergite to apical tergites. Despite the minor differences, the conspecificity of the Korean specimen and the holotype specimen is unequivocal.

Campoletis annulata (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Chann-Pay Plateau, Sam-zi-yan [= Samjiyon], 1700m, 24–25 July 1975, No. 289, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 male. [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, river Karim, 10 km NNE of Bochonbo [= Pochonbo], 1100m, 27 July 1975, No. 297, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 female. [North] Korea, Prov. Pyong-sung, Bek-sung-li, Zamo san [= Chamo Mt.], 60 km NE of Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], 1 August 1975, No. 304, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 female, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017, VAS 2019a, b).

Notes on identification – All the above reported Korean specimens have entirely blackish hind femora and almost entirely black metasoma, which character states are within the known limits of intraspecific variability in

colouration (RIEDEL 2017). However, in the case of both females and one of the males, the usually ivory parts of hind tibia are darker, yellowish brown, therefore the colouration pattern of the hind tibia is much less contrasting than usual. Since these specimens do not differ from *C. annulata* in anything besides the unusually darkened and less contrastingly coloured hind tibia, this difference is concluded as an addition to the known limits of intraspecific variability of the species.

Campoletis chlorideae Uchida, 1957

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Phenan, Bong-ha ri, on the river Te-dong [= Taedong], 45 km N from Pyongyang, 23 May 1970, Hung. Zool. Exp. I. in Korea, No. 19, leg. Dr. S. Mahunka et Dr. H. Steinmann, 1 female. [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyogan, Chang-lyong san, 50 km N of Pyongyan [= Pyongyang], 13. Aug. 1971, No. 169, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female. [North] Korea, Tesson, 35 km SW of Pyongyan [= Pyongyang], waterbasin, 4.VII.1977, No. 343, 344, netting in grasses, [leg.] [O.] Dely & [Á.] Draskovits, 2 females. [North] Korea, Prov. S. Hwanghae, Suyong-san, 28.IX.1978, No. 421, leg. Dr. A. Vojnits et L. Zombori, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species is widely distributed in the Palaeartic and Oriental regions; it is known from South Korea (YU *et al.* 2016, LEE *et al.* 2011).

Campoletis cognata (Tschek, 1871)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Hyesan, Mt. Zedong, 1150m, 26 July 1975, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, No. 293, 1 female, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is widely distributed in the Palaeartic region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017, VAS 2019a).

Campoletis koreana sp. nov.

(Figs 1–2)

Type material – Holotype: female, [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Plateau Chann-Pay, Sam-zi-yan [= Samjiyon], 1700m, 27 Aug. 1971, No. 209, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155168. Paratypes: one male, [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Chann-Pay plateau, 24 km NW from Samziyan [= Samjiyon], road to Mt. Pektusan, 2000m, 24 July 1975,

No. 281, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155169; one male, [North] Korea, Ryanggang Prov., Samjiyon, 3.VI.1985, No. 976, leg. [A.] Vojnits et [L.] Zombori, specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155170. Holotype and paratypes are deposited in the HNHM.

Figures 1–2. *Campoletis koreana* sp. nov., holotype: 1 = lateral habitus, scale bar = 1 mm; 2 = propodeal carination (surface sculpture not indicated)

Diagnosis – The new species can be identified by the following character states in combination: preapical flagellomeres longer than wide; gena distinctly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view in female 0.55 \times , in male 0.65 \times as long as eye width; occipital carina ventrally obsolete; apical margin of clypeus with a distinct, triangular median tooth; malar space 0.5 \times as long as basal width of mandible; speculum finely granulate; area superomedia posteriorly opened, wider than long, its lateral sides behind costulae divergent; fore wing with petiolate areolet, lower external angle of second discal cell acute; inner spur of hind tibia 0.6–0.7 \times as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus; second tergite as long as or slightly longer than its apical width; ovipositor sheath as long as first tergite, 0.6 \times as long as hind tibia; tegula pale yellow; metasoma black; all coxae black; fore and middle femora orange, hind femur black; hind tibia basally and apically dark brown, externo-medially ivory, interno-medially orange.

Description – Female (Figs 1–2). Body length ca. 7 mm, fore wing length ca. 5.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 30–31 flagellomeres; first flagellomere ca. 3.5 \times as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres slightly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, hairs dense and short. Ocular-ocellar distance as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.2 \times as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, about parallel. Gena short, distinctly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.55 \times as long as eye width. Occipital carina

ventrally obsolete, hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons almost flat, median longitudinal carina absent. Face almost flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, flat in profile, its apical margin with a distinct, triangular median tooth. Malar space short, 0.5× as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible wide and short, lower margin with relatively wide flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed before teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma relatively stout, matt, entirely granulate, virtually impunctate (only with some rather weak, barely discernible traces of punctures), and with dense, short hairs. Pronotum with transverse to oblique wrinkles on lower half; epomia distinct. Mesoscutum about as long as wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and moderately deep. Scutellum convex in profile, without lateral carina. Mesopleuron entirely granulate, including the finely granulate speculum, and with a weak, short impression at the anterior part of sternaulus. Epicnemial carina complete, strong, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it slightly below its middle height, transversal part (i.e., the part at the level of sternaulus running through the epicnemium to the ventral edge of pronotum) not developed, ventral part (behind fore coxae) slightly elevated. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, elevated. Metanotum ca. 0.5× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, oval, separated from pleural carina by ca. 1.5× its length, connected to pleural carina by a weak ridge. Propodeum short, convex in profile, granulate with rather weak, mostly transverse rugulosity posteriorly, and posteriorly with a wide median impression. Propodeal carinae: lateromedian longitudinal carina complete, weakened behind costulae; lateral longitudinal carina complete, rather weak but discernible; anterior transverse carina, including costulae, complete; posterior transverse carina only laterally developed, its median section absent. Area basalis triangular, slightly longer than its anterior width. Area superomedia pentagonal, wider than long, its lateral sides behind costulae divergent, posteriorly opened. Area petiolaris confluent with area superomedia, their junction not discernible, medially widely impressed. Fore wing with distinctly petiolate areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) at about middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* long, straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by about its width, inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted slightly below its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) slightly reclivous, weakly broken, intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*) slightly below its middle; discoidella spectral, proximally connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate. Hind femur relatively stout, 4.5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia long, 0.7× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws about as long as arolium, distinctly pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma weakly compressed, matt, very finely granulate to shagreened, impunctate, and with dense, very short hairs. First tergite ca. $2.7\times$ as long as its apical width; glymma strong, deep; dorsomedian carina of first tergite distinct. Second tergite $1.15\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium circular, relatively large, its distance from basal margin of tergite about as long as its length. Posterior margins of apical tergites straight. Ovipositor sheath as long as first tergite, $0.6\times$ as long as hind tibia; ovipositor strong, compressed, distinctly upcurved, dorsal subapical notch distinct.

Colour: Flagellum blackish to dark brown, scapus and pedicellus blackish. Head black, palpi yellowish, mandible brownish yellow, basally narrowly darkened, mandibular teeth brown. Mesosoma black, tegula pale yellow. Metasoma black. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae black; trochanters, trochantelli, femora and tibiae orange, the latter externo-medially more or less pale yellowish; tarsi orange, the apical tarsomeres darkened. Hind leg: coxa black; trochanter and trochantellus blackish, apically very narrowly yellowish brown; femur black, basally very narrowly yellowish brown; tibia basally and apically dark brown, externo-medially ivory, interno-medially orange; tarsus brownish, except basal two-thirds of first tarsomere pale yellowish. Hairs of body greyish.

Male: Similar to female in all characters described above, except: antenna with 32–33 flagellomeres, first flagellomere ca. 2.7 – $2.9\times$ as long as its apical width, preapical flagellomeres more elongate than in female; gena in dorsal view $0.65\times$ as long as eye width; propodeal spiracle slightly larger, separated from pleural carina by about its length; lateromedian and lateral longitudinal carinae of propodeum less weakened behind costulae than in female; area basalis weakly trapezoid; inner spur of hind tibia 0.60 – $0.65\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus; second tergite 1.0 – $1.1\times$ as long as its apical width; claspers wide, apically rounded; pale yellowish colouration of hind tarsus restricted to basal 0.3 – $0.5\times$ length of first tarsomere.

Distribution – North Korea.

Etymology – The specific epithet *koreana* is the feminine form of the Latinised adjective koreanus, -a, -um, meaning Korean.

Remarks on identification – Due to the presence of clypeal tooth, posteriorly opened area superomedia and colouration of hind legs, the new species is most similar to *Campoletis vimmeri* (Gregor, 1938), a species known from several countries of Europe; and, by using the identification key to the Western Palearctic *Campoletis* species in RIEDEL (2017), the new species keys out with this species at couplet 11 (without complete match to the characters listed in the couplet). *Campoletis vimmeri* can be easily distinguished from the new species by the following: its ovipositor sheath is significantly longer (1.5 – $1.6\times$ as long as first tergite, 0.9 – $1.0\times$ as long as hind tibia), second tergite is distinctly transverse (ca. $0.75\times$ as long as its apical width), inner spur of hind tibia is shorter (at most $0.5\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus); gena is longer (in dorsal view $0.8\times$ as

long as eye width), areolet is subsessile, and the preapical flagellomeres of females are transverse. By using the identification key to the *Campoletis* species known from China, South Korea and Japan in WEI *et al.* (2020), the new species keys out at couplet 8 with *Campoletis takizawai* Kusigemati, 1972, a species known from Japan; however, this species cannot be confused with the new species due to its reddish hind femur and basally ivory hind tibia.

Campoletis latrator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Hyesan, Hotel garden, 23. Aug. 1971, No. 193, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female. [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, river Karim, 10 km NNE of Bochonbo [= Pochonbo], 27 July 1975, No. 296, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is known from several countries of the Western Palaearctic region, while from the Eastern Palaearctic region it was reported from Iran and Mongolia (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017, VAS 2019b); hence, the present records represent the easternmost known localities of the distribution of the species.

Notes on identification – The above reported Korean female specimen, similarly to the female specimen reported from Mongolia by VAS (2019b), shows minor differences as compared to the other examined, Western Palaearctic specimens and to the characteristics given in the latest revision of the genus (RIEDEL 2017): the fore and middle coxae are dark, while these are predominantly reddish in other specimens; the ovipositor sheath is slightly shorter, its length is 0.45× length of hind tibia, and 0.75× length of first tergite, while 0.5–0.6× length of hind tibia, and 0.85–0.95× length of first tergite in other specimens. Otherwise, these Korean and Mongolian specimens are very similar in all important characteristics, therefore it is concluded that they rather represent additional information to the intraspecific variability than an undescribed species. The above reported Korean male is a typical specimen.

Campoletis rugosipropodeum (Uchida, 1942)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], city park, 4. Aug. 1971, No. 137, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 3 females, 18 males. [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 7–8. Aug. 1971, No. 150, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 2 females, 2 males. Same locality and collectors, 10. Aug. 1971, No. 157, 2 females. Same locality and collectors, 11. Aug. 1971, No. 162, 6 females, 1 male. Same locality and collectors, 12. Aug. 1971, No. 166, 2 males. [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Chang-lyong san, 50 km N of Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], 13.

Aug. 1971, No. 169, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 3 females. [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], city park, 14. Aug. 1971, No. 176, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female, 3 males. Same locality and collectors, 15. Aug. 1971, No. 177, 1 female, 5 males. Same locality and collectors, 20–21. Aug. 1971, No. 190, 5 females, 1 male. Same locality and collectors, 23. Aug. 1971, No. 193, 5 males. [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], garden of Hungarian Embassy, 16–18 July 1975, No. 266, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 female. [North] Korea, Prov. Gang-von [= Kangwon], district On-dzong [= Kosŏng, Onjong-ri], Kum-gang san, near Hotel Go-song, 250 m, No. 326, 6–8 August 1975, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 male.

Remarks – First records for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species was described and known from China (Liaoning) (UCHIDA 1942, YU *et al.* 2016).

Notes on identification – The fore and middle coxae of the male specimens are more or less yellowish, especially ventrally, which should be kept in mind while using the identification key in WEI *et al.* (2020) to avoid misidentification of males.

Campoplex alsophilae (Uchida, 1936)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongan [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 31 Aug. 1971, No. 225, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 3 males. Same locality and collectors, 1 Sept. 1971, No. 229, 2 males.

Remarks – First records for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species was described and known hitherto only from Japan (UCHIDA 1936, YU *et al.* 2016).

Casinaria albibasalis Uchida, 1928

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. S. Pyongan, Taesong-ho, 26.IX.1978, No. 406, leg. Dr. A. Vojnits et L. Zombori, 1 female. [North] Korea, Pyongyang, [Mt.] Daesong-san, 10 km NE of the city, 09.07.1982, No. 760, leg. Dr. L. Forró and Dr. L. Ronkay, 1 male.

Remarks – First records for North Korea. This species is known from the Eastern Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016), and was reported from South Korea (CHOI & LEE 2010, LEE *et al.* 2011).

Casinaria albipalpis (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Gang-von [= Kangwon], district On-dzong [= Kosöng, Onjong-ri], Kum-gang san, near Hotel Go-song, 250 m, No. 315, 4 August 1975, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 male. Same locality and collectors, No. 322, 6 August 1975, 1 male.

Remarks – First records for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic region, and was also found in the eastern parts of Russia (Primorsky Krai) (YU *et al.* 2016).

Casinaria arjuna Maheshwary et Gupta, 1977

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Hyesan, Hotel garden, 23. Aug. 1971, No. 193, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species is known from the Oriental and Eastern Palaearctic regions (YU *et al.* 2016), and was reported from South Korea (CHOI & LEE 2010, LEE *et al.* 2011).

Casinaria japonica Kusigemati, 1980

Material examined – [North] Korea, Kaesong, Mts. Pakyon, Pakyon popo, 27 km NE from Kaesong, 9. Sept. 1971, No. 249, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 male. Same locality and collectors, 10–12. Sept. 1971, No. 257, 1 male. [North] Korea, Do Samg-san, 10 km NE Pyongyang, 1.VII.1977, No. 333, Malaise trap, leg. [O.] Dely & [Á.] Draskovits, 1 female.

Remarks – First records for North Korea. This species was described from Japan, and was also found in South Korea (CHOI & LEE 2010, LEE *et al.* 2011, YU *et al.* 2016).

Casinaria nigripes (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyogan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 12. Aug. 1971, No. 166, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 male. Same locality, 28.07.1982, No. 871, leg. Dr. L. Forró and Dr. L. Ronkay, 1 female.

Remarks – First records for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic and Oriental regions (YU *et al.* 2016).

Casinaria partolstoji Han, van Achterberg et Chen, 2021

Material examined – [North] Korea, Mt. Pektusan, environs Sam-zi-yan [= Samjiyon], hotel, 18–20.VII.1977, No. 374, netting in grasses, leg. [O.] Dely & [Á.] Draskovits, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species was recently described from China (Xinjiang) (HAN *et al.* 2021a).

Casinaria stygia Tschek, 1871

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. North Pyongan, Mt. Myohyangsan, Hyangsan, 15.IX.1980., No. 680, leg. [L.] Forró and & [Gy.] Topál, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Eastern Palaearctic region). This species is known from several countries of the Western Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018a, VAS 2019c); the Korean specimen represents the first record from the Eastern Palaearctic region, significantly expanding the known distribution of the species.

Casinaria trochanterator Aubert, 1960

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 12. Aug. 1971, No. 166, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 male. [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Hyesan, Hotel garden, 23. Aug. 1971, No. 193, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 2 males.

Remarks – First records for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic region, and was also reported from Iran (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018a, VAS 2018, 2019c).

Charops bicolor (Szépligeti, 1906)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Lyong-ak san, 25 km W from Pyongan [= Pyongyang], 10 August 1971, No. 158, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species is widely distributed in the Eastern Palaearctic and Oriental regions (YU *et al.* 2016), and was reported from South Korea (CHOI & LEE 2008, LEE *et al.* 2011).

Charops striatus (Uchida, 1932)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 6–7 September 1971, No. 243, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species is widely distributed in the Eastern Palaearctic and Oriental regions (YU *et al.* 2016), and was reported from South Korea (CHOI & LEE 2008, LEE *et al.* 2011).

Cymodusa koreana Choi et Lee, 2013

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Phenan, Sa-gam po, 30 km N from Pyongyang, 24 May 1970, Hung. Zool. Exp. I. in Korea, No. 28, leg. Dr. S. Mahunka et Dr. H. Steinmann, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species was described and known from South Korea (CHOI *et al.* 2013, YU *et al.* 2016).

Cymodusa orientalis Uchida, 1956

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Plateau Chann-Pay, Sam-zi-yan [= Samjiyon], 1500m, 24 August 1971, No. 196, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species is known from the Oriental and Eastern Palaearctic regions (YU *et al.* 2016), and was recorded from South Korea by CHOI *et al.* (2013) as *Cymodusa aenigma* Dbar, 1985, which name was recently synonymised with *Cymodusa orientalis* Uchida, 1956 (WATANABE 2020).

Lemophagus curtus Townes, 1965

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongyang [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 6–7 September 1971, No. 243, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region (HORSTMANN 2004, YU *et al.* 2016).

Melalophacharops everese (Uchida, 1957)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. South Pyongan, Pyongan [= Pyongyang], Hotel garden, 31 Aug. 1971, No. 225, leg. S. Horvatovich et J. Papp, 1 female. [North] Korea, North Pyongan Prov., Mt. Myohyang-san, Hyangsan, 1994.IX.19., leg. Mészáros F. & Zombori L., 1 female. [North] Korea, Kangwon Prov., Mt. Kungang-san, Oe Kungang, 1994.IX.25., leg. Mészáros F. & Zombori L., 1 female.

Remarks – First records for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species was described and known from Japan (UCHIDA 1957, KUSIGEMATI 1967, YU *et al.* 2016), and was recently reported from Taiwan (VAS 2023).

Meloboris pektusana sp. nov.

(Figs 3–4)

Type material – Holotype: female, [North] Korea, Prov. Ryang-gang, Chann-Pay plateau, Mt. Pektusan, Mu-do-bong, 2100–2200m, 25 July 1975, No. 288, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155171. Paratype: one female, same label data, specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155172. Holotype and paratype are deposited in the HNHM.

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Figures 3–4. *Meloboris pektusana* sp. nov., holotype: 1 = lateral habitus, scale bar = 1 mm; 2 = propodeal carination (surface sculpture not indicated)

Diagnosis – The new species can be identified by the following character states in combination: first tergite stout with strong glymmae; ocular-ocellar distance $1.5\times$ as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli as long as ocellus diameter; gena in dorsal view $0.60\text{--}0.65\times$ as long as eye width, roundly narrowed behind eyes; inner eye orbits convergent ventrad; clypeus subapically convex in profile; malar space $0.6\text{--}0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible; mesopleuron entirely granulate, wrinkles anterior to speculum nearly absent; area superomedia $2.6\text{--}2.9\times$ as long as wide, its lateral sides behind costulae parallel to subparallel, posteriorly opened or very weakly closed; postnervulus intercepted distinctly above its middle; second tergite $1.4\times$ as long as its apical width; antenna brown, except pedicellus ventrally yellowish; metasoma blackish to dark brown, posterior margins of tergites (except first tergite) narrowly yellowish brown; hind femur dark brown; hind tibia orange to orange-brown, subbasally very weakly, apically moderately darkened, externo-medially and basally slightly paler.

Description – Female (Figs 3–4). Body length ca. 3.5 mm, fore wing length ca. 3 mm.

Head: Antenna with 25 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, ca. $5\times$ as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres slightly longer than wide, penultimate flagellomere ca. $1.4\times$ as long as wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, hairs dense and moderately short. Ocular-ocellar distance $1.5\times$ as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, distinctly convergent ventrad. Gena distinctly but moderately strongly, roundly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view $0.60\text{--}0.65\times$ as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina little before base of mandible, hypostomal carina not elevated. Frons weakly convex, without median longitudinal carina. Face almost flat in profile, narrowed ventrad, minimum width of face ca. $0.75\times$ as long as maximum width of frons. Clypeus weakly separated from face, subapically distinctly convex in profile, its apical margin subtruncate, sharp. Malar space $0.6\text{--}0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with relatively narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed before teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma distinctly elongate, matt, entirely granulate, virtually impunctate (at most with some rather weak, barely discernible traces of punctures on mesoscutum), and with dense, short hairs. Pronotum with transverse wrinkles on lower half; epomia weak. Mesoscutum ca. $1.25\times$ as long as wide, convex in profile; notaulus indistinct. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and moderately deep. Scutellum convex in profile, without lateral carina. Mesopleuron entirely granulate, wrinkles anterior to speculum barely discernible, nearly absent; speculum finely granulate. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it slightly below its middle height. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum obsolete before middle coxae. Metanotum ca. $0.4\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron relatively

elongate, without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, subcircular, adjacent to pleural carina. Propodeum elongate, convex in profile, entirely granulate, posteriorly with rather weak, indistinct rugulosity. Propodeal carinae: lateromedian and lateral longitudinal carinae complete; anterior transverse carina incomplete, medially present, costulae obsolete or virtually absent; posterior transverse carina laterally strongly developed, medially obsolete or virtually absent. Area basalis elongate, narrow trapezoid, distinctly longer than its anterior width, posteriorly closed. Area superomedia elongate, $2.6-2.9\times$ as long as wide, its lateral sides behind costulae parallel to subparallel, posteriorly opened or very weakly, indistinctly closed, the junction with area petiolaris distinct. Fore wing with shortly sessile, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* almost straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by about twice of its width, strongly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted distinctly above its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell almost right-angled. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) weakly reclivous, intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*) at about its middle; discoidella spectral, proximally connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate. Hind femur $4.5-4.8\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia $0.45-0.50\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws thin, about as long as arolium, basally weakly pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma moderately compressed, matt, finely granulate to shagreened, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite stout, ca. $2.4\times$ as long as its apical width; glymma strong, deep; dorsomedian carina of first tergite discernible. Second tergite $1.4\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium subcircular to oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite $1.5-1.8\times$ as long as its length. Posterior margins of apical tergites medially slightly concave, almost straight. Ovipositor sheath short, about as long as apical depth of metasoma; ovipositor straight.

Colour: Antenna, including scapus, brown, pedicellus ventrally brownish yellow. Head black, palpi and mandible pale yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula pale yellow. Metasoma blackish to dark brown, posterior margins of tergites (except first tergite) narrowly yellowish brown. Wings hyaline, wing veins brownish, pterostigma yellowish brown. Fore leg: coxa basally blackish, apically brownish; trochanter and trochantellus pale yellow; femur, tibia and tarsus pale orange, apical tarsomere darkened. Middle leg similar to fore leg, except femur more or less extensively brownish. Hind leg: coxa black; trochanter predominantly brownish; trochantellus pale yellow; femur dark brown; tibia orange to orange-brown, subbasally very weakly, apically moderately darkened, externo-medially and basally slightly paler; tarsus brownish. Hairs of body greyish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – North Korea.

Etyymology – The specific epithet *pektusana* is the feminine form of the Latinised adjective *pektusanus*, -a, -um, referring to the type locality.

Remarks on identification – Due to the rather stout first tergite and strong glymmae, the new species belongs to the “*Meloboris* s. str.” group sensu HORSTMANN (1970, 2004). By using the identification key in the latest revision of the group (HORSTMANN 2004), the new species keys out with *Meloboris dimicatellae* Horstmann, 2004, a European species known from Slovakia, Poland and Germany (HORSTMANN 2004, RIEDEL 2018b). *Meloboris dimicatellae* can be readily distinguished from the new species by its different postnervulus (intercepted at middle), area superomedia (its lateral sides strongly convergent behind costulae), mostly smooth speculum, ventrally yellowish scapus, and basally darkened hind tibia.

Venturia longipropodeum (Uchida, 1942)

Material examined – [North] Korea, Prov. Gang-von [= Kangwon], district On-dzong [= Kosŏng, Onjong-ri], Kum-gang san, near Hotel Go-song, No. 325, 7 August 1975, leg. J. Papp et A. Vojnits, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea. This species is known from China and South Korea (UCHIDA 1942, CHOI *et al.* 2012, YU *et al.* 2016, CHOI 2022).

Notes on identification – HAN *et al.* (2021b) erroneously indicate in their identification key (at couplet 6) that the distance between lateral ocelli and ocular-ocellar distance is equal in this species; this cannot be treated as a distinguishing character, in fact the distance between lateral ocelli is 1.3–1.9× as long as ocular-ocellar distance (ca. 1.6× in the holotype specimen).

Venturia mongolica (Kokujev, 1915)

Material examined – [North] Korea, North Hamgyong Prov., Musan [County], 19–20.8.1998, leg. Han Bing Hi, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for North Korea (and for the Korean Peninsula). This species is known from the Eastern Palaearctic part of China (KOKUJEV 1915, YU *et al.* 2016) and from Mongolia (VAS 2019b).

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**„Visszatérés” Észak-Koreába:
a Campopleginae alcsalád új fajai és előfordulási adatai
(Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)**

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Összefoglalás – 1970 és 1995 között a Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum kutatói húsz észak-koreai gyűjtőexpedícióban vettek részt. A begyűjtött valódi fürkészdarázsok (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) döntő részben még meghatározásra várnak. Jelen munkában a Campopleginae alcsaládból két tudományra új fürkészdarázsfaj (*Campoletis koreana* sp. nov. és *Meloboris pektusana* sp. nov.) leírását, illetve a következő 23 fürkészdarázsfaj első észak-koreai előfordulási adatait közli a szerző: *Breviterebra laticlypeata* Kusigemati, 1982, *Campoletis annulata* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Campoletis chlorideae* Uchida, 1957, *Campoletis cognata* (Tschek, 1871), *Campoletis latrator* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Campoletis rugosipropodeum* (Uchida, 1942), *Campoplex alsophilae* (Uchida, 1936), *Casinaria albibasalis* Uchida, 1928, *Casinaria albipalpis* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Casinaria arjuna* Maheshwary et Gupta, 1977, *Casinaria japonica* Kusigemati, 1980, *Casinaria nigripes* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Casinaria partolstoyi* Han, van Achterberg et Chen, 2021, *Casinaria stygia* Tschek, 1871, *Casinaria trochanterator* Aubert, 1960, *Charops bicolor* (Szépligeti, 1906), *Charops striatus* (Uchida, 1932), *Cymodusa koreana* Choi et Lee, 2013, *Cymodusa orientalis* Uchida, 1956, *Lemophagus curtus* Townes, 1965, *Melalophacharops everese* (Uchida, 1957), *Venturia longipropodeum* (Uchida, 1942) és *Venturia mongolica* (Kokujev, 1915). Négy ábrával.

Kulcsszavak – taxonómia, fajleírás, biogeográfia, Koreai-félsziget

ÁBRAMAGYARÁZATOK

1–2. ábra. *Campoletis koreana* sp. nov., holotípus: 1 = habitus, oldalnézet, méretléc = 1 mm; 2 = propodeum

3–4. ábra. *Meloboris pektusana* sp. nov., holotípus: 1 = habitus, oldalnézet, méretléc = 1 mm; 2 = propodeum